

Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA

Version 0

Description

Recently we have developed a peptide nucleic acid (PNA) and double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) triplex computational model. Implementation of molecular dynamics simulations, based on our triplex model resulted in discovery of original and effective PNA nucleobase for recognition of CG base pair in RNA. During the course of PhD research, we are planning to further develop computational techniques for the design of more selective PNA nucleobases with higher affinity and stability at physiological pH. The main goal is to create a universal set of PNA nucleobases for recognition of any dsRNA base pair in any dsRNA sequence. This will allow to create an important tool for molecular recognition of regulatory RNA and to control its biological functions.

Funder

Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grant

Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA

Researchers

Vladislavs Baškevičs (orcid:0000-0001-5489-6760)

Organizations
Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA](#)

Description:

Recently we have developed a peptide nucleic acid (PNA) and double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) triplex computational model. Implementation of molecular dynamics simulations, based on our triplex model resulted in discovery of original and effective PNA nucleobase for recognition of CG base pair in RNA. During the course of PhD research, we are planning to further develop computational techniques for the design of more selective PNA nucleobases with higher affinity and stability at physiological pH. The main goal is to create a universal set of PNA nucleobases for recognition of any dsRNA base pair in any dsRNA sequence. This will allow to create an important tool for molecular recognition of regulatory RNA and to control its biological functions.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

[Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis](#)

Contact: [Vladislavs Baškevičs](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Central Finance and Contracting Agency](#)

Grants: [Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA](#)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[Molecular dynamics data](#)

Chrodinger Desmond input/output files used for modeling of certain PNA nucleobases

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data was generated by Schrodinger 2022-4 software package to provide insights into behavior of dsRNA-PNA triplex on a molecular level.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Computational data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

others

.7z

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Computational chemists

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

This is raw data

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

This is unique raw data of computational model, which is not published anywhere. Access is granted upon request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Schrodinger Maestro, WinRar

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-01-01

End term of the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Vladislavs Baškevičs (orcid:0000-0001-5489-6760)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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